

Water Quality Prediction Using Machine Learning

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Abstract— Water is the one of the most leading factors for all the living organism on our earth. Now a days many factors causes the quality of the water is decreases The Objective of this study is to apply the machine learning technique such as Support vector machine(SVM) and Decision Tree Algorithms. To analysis the accuracy of water quality with both these algorithms. This paper focus on the comparative study of SVM and Decision Tree Classifier on water quality prediction. Two different types of dataset is used to evaluated the performance of the models. The both dataset contains the different elements of water.

Keywords:

Python Programming, Machine Learning Algorithms:- SVM, Decision Tree Classifier.

I. INTRODUCTION

Machine learning is an artificial intelligence branch that aims to improve performance over time and uncover patterns in large amounts of data. Water-based data is distinct from other types of data since it includes a wide range of properties and factors. Furthermore, the data may have known flaws, such as missing, erroneous, or insufficient information. For this type of data, machine learning approaches are ideal. Machine learning is increasingly being used to improve water quality in industry, where manual error may be decreased and accuracy improved by computer analysis. Machine learning techniques are extremely accurate in predicting quality.

Human health and the environment are both affected by water quality. Water is used in many different ways, including for drinking, agriculture, and industry. The growth of water entertainment has helped to attract a large number of tourists. Rivers have been employed more frequently for the establishment of societies than other sources of water because of their ease of access. Using alternative water sources, such as groundwater and seawater, can occasionally cause issues. Using groundwater without adequate recharge, for example, will result in soil subsidence, and using seawater is frequently connected with pollution transfer. As a result, the utilisation of rivers has gotten a lot of attention. Several examinations into rivers have been done around the world, and a field of engineering known as river engineering has been proposed.

Machine learning techniques are create an impact on water quality prediction. Because now technologies are build lots of influences in daily life things. Different types water components are handle by SVM algorithm and Decision Tree Classifiers. Each algorithm provide a each level of accuracy and classification reports. These types of technique helps to generate clarification of water quality.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Yafra Khan & Chai Soo See, Predicting and analyzing water quality using machine learning a comprehensive model [2016] [1].

This paper pointed the water quality prediction using ANN and time analysis, focus on water quality parameters like concentration of chlorophyll, dissolved oxygen etc. Four ANN models and four selected water quality parameters has been analyzed. Artificial Neural Network and nonlinear auto regressive time series used. So it helps the prediction part as well as the accuracy part of the water quality.

Zhao Fu, Water Quality Prediction Based on Machine Learning Techniques [professional papers -2020].[2].

This paper discuss the machine learning techniques, that is multivariate linear regression and artificial neural network. Simple linear regression is not used in this analysis, because simple linear is not accurate to display the water quality. Also used Adaptive Neuro- Fuzzy inference System (ANFIS). It the tool which formulating the relationship between linear and non-linear hidden in dataset. So that this model can achieve better performance in the water quality prediction. Several method to be implemented to improve the performance of the model. Because ANFIS model have some limitations.

1. Size of training dataset should not less than the number of training dataset.
2. Testing dataset is not reflected in the training dataset.
3. Strong correlation is required. If the correlation is weak then the model is not accurately display the hidden relationship.

S.Vijay & Dr.K.Kamaraj, Ground Water Quality Prediction using Machine Learning Algorithms in R[2019] [3].

This paper mainly focus on predicting water quality by using Machine Learning classifier algorithms C5.0, Naïve Bayes and Random forest. Calculating the accuracy and efficiency of ground water with nine parameters.

Jitha P Nair & Vijaya M S, Predictive models for river water quality using machine learning [2021][4].

In this paper deals with the advanced big data technique and machine learning technique used to implemented the water quality prediction. Various time series analysis and deep learning technique includes evaluating water quality.

Maqbool Ali, Ali Mustafa Qamar, Data Analysis, Quality Indexing and Prediction of Water Quality for the Management of Rawal Watershed in Pakistan[2013] [5].

In contrast to just controlling water quality at the command level water quality in the locations where water is consumed should also be prioritised. The watersheds are where water is produced. Failure to take action As a result, the water quality in downstream streams deteriorates, posing a threat. Substantial issues for water managers to meet the targets criteria for water quality on a long-term basis To be successful, It is critical to have appropriate water management in command regions. Rawal's watershed is a very small watershed that is impacted by urbanisation, deforestation, and other human activities, hence it is used to assess numerous aspects of water quality. We look at trends over the last four years (2009–2012) in this study. The supervised learning technique Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) has been found to be more accurate.

III. MOTIVATION

Dissolved oxygen concentrations, microbial levels, salt content (or salinity), and the quantity of debris suspended in the water are all elements that affect water quality (turbidity). To estimate water quality, the amount of microscopic algae, as well as the amounts of pesticides, herbicides, heavy metals, and other contaminants, can be measured in various bodies of water. Poor water quality can be harmful to people's health. The health of ecosystems can also be threatened by poor water quality. The Biggest Factors that Affect Water Quality

- Sedimentation.
- Runoff.
- Erosion.
- Dissolved oxygen.
- pH.
- Temperature.
- Pesticides.
- Detergents.

Effects on Human Health

- Health effects of chemical exposure.
- Consuming water with disease-causing microbes.

Figure.1: Heatmap

Heatmap shows the correlation of water components. It contains different shades of colors.

Darker shade represented high values and lighter shade represented low values as compare to the higher values.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Source

The dataset are collected from Kaggle .There are two types of datasets used. First dataset contains ten water components and 3229 data values. Second datasets includes 21 water elements and 8000 data values. Second dataset is large as compare to first dataset. So that large dataset provide a high accuracy rate.

B. Decision tree Classifier

The algorithm decision tree is a strategy for solving classification problems that uses supervised learning. It's essentially a tree-structured algorithm with three nodes. The first starting node is called root node, that include the dataset. Second node is decision node contains decision rules. This node is also called branch node. Final node of the decision tree is leaf node it have no further braches.

a) *Algorithm 1:* Water Quality prediction using Decision Tree classifier. [Use Two type dataset]

Step 1: Read the dataset.

Step 2: Exploratory Data Analysis: Describe the data, plotting the data(box plot,countplot,heatmap etc.)

Step 3: Train Decision Tree Classifier and check accuracy.

Step 4: Apply Hyper parameter tuning.

Step5:Perform the cross validation by using GridSearchCV()

b) *Experimental Results:* Firstly the decision tree classifier perform the ten featured dataset to produce an accuracy(59.75%) , precision(0.67) and recall(0.69). Secondally the classifier decision tree model with 21 featured dataset to display the accuracy(96%), precision (0.91) and recall(0.93).

C. Support Vector Machine(SVM)

Support vector machine is a most usable supervised learning technique. It is used for classification problems. The main aim of this algorithm is to create a decision boundary that can be separated into n dimensional space into classes. So we can simply put the new data point in the correct groups in the future. Consider the best decision boundary is called hyperplane. This algorithm is relatively memory efficient.

SVM are element points that are closer to the hyperplane and it influences the arrangement of hyperplane. Use this algorithm to maximize the classifier margin. SVM is highly recommended by many as it distributes significant accuracy with less computational power.

a) *Algorithm 2:* Water Quality prediction using Support Vector Machine. [Use Two type dataset]

Step 1: Read the datasets.

Step 2: Split the train and test data and fit the model.

Step 3: Find out the accuracy of the model.

Step 4: Generate the confusion matrix, precision and recall.

b) *Experimental Results:* According to the two type datasets, ten featured dataset provide an accuracy of 59.75%, precision(0.67) and recall(0.69)

Second, 21 field dataset implies an accuracy of 88%. Precision.

Accuracy is improved when the dataset become more number of features and contains large data values.

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Figure.2: Flow of methodology.

After data preprocessing perform `train_test_split()` function is used. Sklearn model selection has a method called `train_test_split()` that splits data arrays into two subsets: training data and testing data. You don't have to divide the dataset manually with this function. Sklearn `train_test_split()` creates random divisions for the two subsets by default.

Cross validation: GridSearchCV is a technique for finding the optimal parameter values from a given set of parameters in a grid. It's essentially a cross-validation technique. The model as well as the parameters must be entered. After extracting the best parameter values, predictions are made.

Hyper parameter tuning is the process of finding the best combination of hyper parameters to improve model performance (or hyper parameter optimization). It works by condensing multiple trials into a single session of training. Each trial is a full run of your training program with values for your selected hyper parameters set within the parameters you choose. You'll have a collection of hyper parameter values that are most suited for the model to deliver optimum results once you've finished this process.

V. BUILD MODEL

Main step of the implementation is done by Decision Tree.

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
```

Figure.3: Import packages.

```
plt.figure(figsize=(13,8))
sns.heatmap(df.corr(),annot=True,cmap='terrain')
plt.show()
```

Figure.4: Create a heatmap to analyze correlation.

```
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
X_train, X_test, Y_train, Y_test = train_test_split(X,Y, test_size= 0.2, random_state=101,shuffle=True)

from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeClassifier
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score,confusion_matrix,classification_report
dt=DecisionTreeClassifier(criterion= 'gini', min_samples_split= 10, splitter= 'best')
dt.fit(X_train,Y_train)
```

Figure.5: Split train and test data, fit the model

```
prediction=dt.predict(X_test)
print(f"Accuracy Score = {accuracy_score(Y_test,prediction)*100}")
print(f"Confusion Matrix =\n {confusion_matrix(Y_test,prediction)}")
print(f"Classification Report =\n {classification_report(Y_test,prediction)}")
```

Figure.6: Predict the model

```

from sklearn.model_selection import RepeatedStratifiedKFold
from sklearn.model_selection import GridSearchCV

# define models and parameters
model = DecisionTreeClassifier()
criterion = ["gini", "entropy"]
splitter = ["best", "random"]
min_samples_split = [2,4,6,8,10,12,14]

# define grid search
grid = dict(splitter=splitter, criterion=criterion, min_samples_split=min_samples_split)
cv = RepeatedStratifiedKFold(n_splits=10, n_repeats=3, random_state=1)
grid_search_dt = GridSearchCV(estimator=model, param_grid=grid, n_jobs=-1, cv=cv,
                              scoring='accuracy', error_score=0)
grid_search_dt.fit(X_train, Y_train)
    
```

Figure.7: Perform the cross validation procedure.

```

print(f"Best: {grid_search_dt.best_score_:.3f} using {grid_search_dt.best_params}")
means = grid_search_dt.cv_results_['mean_test_score']
stds = grid_search_dt.cv_results_['std_test_score']
params = grid_search_dt.cv_results_['params']

for mean, stdev, param in zip(means, stds, params):
    print(f"mean: {mean:.3f} (stdev: {stdev:.3f}) with: {param}")

print("Training Score:", grid_search_dt.score(X_train, Y_train)*100)
print("Testing Score:", grid_search_dt.score(X_test, Y_test)*100)
    
```

Figure 8: Apply the hyper parameter tuning.

VI. RESULT

Algorithm	Dataset	Accuracy
Decision Tree Classifier	Small	59%
Decision Tree Classifier	Large	96%
SVM	Small	59%
SVM	Large	88%

Table.1: Comparison of accuracies with different algorithms

VII. CONCLUSION

In this research provide the comparison of two machine learning techniques such as SVM and Decision tree. But In the case of using SVM with large dataset to produce the accuracy is 88% and use of Decision tree classifier to get 96% of accuracy. This implies that the improvement of accuracy affects:

- Large number of data values
- Large number of Fields
- Different types of algorithm we used.

classifier. Use SVM with Small amount of dataset to produce the accuracy is 59%. Same accuracy is obtained by using the Decision tree.

REFERENCES

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